

IMPACT OF MICROCREDIT ON ASSET BASE AND INCOME GENERATING ACTIVITIES OF THE POOR IN OSUN STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract: The study empirically examined the impact of the micro intervention funds on the asset base and income-generating activities of beneficiaries in Osun State, Nigeria. Primary data were collected through questionnaires, structured interviews and focus group discussions with secondary sources. Descriptive statistics such as frequency distribution and percentages were used in the data analysis. Appropriate descriptive and analytical tools were employed to process the obtained data. The results of the study established that the intervention was successful in terms of strengthening the asset base and promoting the beneficiaries' income-generating activities. In other words, access to micro-credit has a positive but insignificant impact on poverty alleviation among the rural population. In conclusion, the intervention was successful in strengthening the asset base and promoting the beneficiaries' income-generating activities. The study recommends that microcredit organizations should collect data from their clients on entry, which could be used as baseline information for later impact assessment. Impact assessment should be institutionalized and be an ongoing exercise rather than a one-off post-mortem event.

Keywords: Microcredit, Impact, Asset base, Income generating activities, Poor

Introduction

Literature Review

Over the past two decades, policymakers, international development agencies, and non-government organizations have devised various developmental approaches aimed at poverty reduction in developing countries. One of the most popular strategies, especially since the early 1990s, is the micro-credit scheme, which provides credit opportunities to the working poor (Tria *et al.*, 2022). The use of microcredit to fight poverty is supported by empirical literature that access to it facilitates the adoption of modern production technologies and overall household welfare (Akudugu, 2012; Félix *et al.*, 2019).

Microcredit is a small loan given to a client to enable them to engage in productive business activities. It is usually not backed by collateral (Abebe and Kegne, 2023). Although the desirability of a multi-faceted approach to poverty eradication is generally accepted, given the multi-dimensional nature of poverty (e.g., lack of food, education, health, shelter, security, and credit), micro-credit seems to have been globally recognized as the most potent weapon to combat poverty (Awojobi, 2019). This is based on the belief that other indices of poverty eradication can only function successfully under a sustainable income generation. The philosophy is that what

the poor need is not charity or gifts but, credit, a helping hand in the form of microcredit, practical training, and market opportunities that will enable them to walk out of poverty with dignity. The philosophy, therefore, rests on the principle of giving people back their dignity by de-emphasizing charity and upholding economic empowerment. This is because charity does not create discipline but creates and encourages continuous dependency (Yin *et al.*, 2023).

The practice of microcredit/microfinance in most African studies is culturally rooted and dates back several centuries. Traditional microfinance institutions provide access to credit for rural and urban low-income earners. They are mainly informal self-help Groups (SHG) or rotating savings and credit association (ROSCA) types. Others include savings, collectors, and cooperative societies. Microcredit is called by various names in various cultures ‘esusu’ ‘bam’, ‘adashi’, ‘ajo’. The general problem is that they have limited outreach primarily because of the paucity of loanable funds.

Access to credit has been identified as one of the key factors required to accelerate growth and improve welfare in developing countries. There is a need to intensify efforts in making credit accessible to households since such a strategy will liberate a greater percentage of the population from poverty, encourage savings, and improve investment in physical and human capital, which promotes economic growth. The poor’s latent capacity for entrepreneurship would be significantly enhanced through the provision of credit facilities to enable them to engage in economic activities and be more self-reliant; increase employment opportunities, and create wealth (CBN, 2005). This lack of adequate access to credit has significant negative consequences for various aggregate and household-level outcomes, such as technology adoption, agricultural productivity, food security, nutrition, health, and overall household welfare (Salima *et al.*, 2023). Improved access to credit will help poor rural households to engage in more productive income-generating activities that will raise their living standards.

In 2004, the Osun State Government, with collaborative support from UNDP, embarked on specifically designed strategies for poverty alleviation in the state by drawing up a four-cardinal Blueprint document. The four components of the blueprint are as follows: agriculture and agro-allied industrial development, microcredit, job creation and social development. The program was called the UNDP/Osun State Sustainable Human Development Fund **program**.

Two of the major objectives of the microcredit component of the scheme are as follows:

- (i) strengthen the asset base and economic livelihood of the economically challenged population,
- (ii) promote income-generating activities and improve credit facility access.

Overall, a total of ₦30 million was made available under this program. The fund was disbursed to approximately 4,000 beneficiaries through 117 trade and artisan groups **among** 4,000 beneficiaries between November 2004 and February 2005. By the time this study was carried out in 2023/2024, the loan had gone around eight times.

Statement of the problem

Most studies on microcredit, such as Tria *et al.* (2022) and Félix *et al.* (2019), evaluate microcredit based on repayment and disbursements indicators. The assumption is that the scheme is successful if the repayment rate is high. This is, to say the least, a pro-lender evaluation method and can be misleading because high repayment loans or effective disbursement methods are not directly related to the success of borrowers’ businesses or the impact on their socioeconomic lives. This is because borrowers could have repaid the loan from sources of income other than the business in which the loan was invested.

Such pro-lender studies are concerned with microfinance institution's measures of profitability and portfolio quality. While these are important measures of an organization's institutional health they do not measure client health or well-being (Kruk *et al.*, 2018).

The UNDP/OSSHDF microcredit scheme achieved a 98% recovery rate, and it was adjudged a success by the donors (Todaro, 2008). However, various questions remain unanswered on the extent to which the intervention positively impacted poverty alleviation, which was the scheme's main objective. No study was conducted to determine the extent to which the set objectives of the intervention were achieved. Unless this is done, determining the success or otherwise of the intervention in terms of its set objectives as well as the overall objective of poverty alleviation would be difficult. Such a study is also essential for identifying areas of the scheme's weakness/strength that could lead to improvement in future intervention programs.

Against this background, this study measures the impact of microcredit intervention on the asset base and income-generating activities beneficiaries.

Purpose and Relevance of the Study

This study aims to measure the impact of the N30 million micro-credit intervention fund on the asset base and income-generating activities of the beneficiaries and to determine the effects of the intervention on the lives of the people of Osun State. Access to credit is one of the core factors considered in determining the level of inequality and poverty, especially in developing countries such as Nigeria. Therefore, improved access to credit will help poor households to engage in more productive income-generating activities that will improve their living standards.

Hypotheses

Two null hypotheses were developed and tested:

- (i) Microcredit does not lead to improvement in beneficiaries' asset base.
- (ii) Microcredit does not lead to improvement in beneficiaries' income-generating activities.

Methodology

Population analysis, sample selection, and procedure

The study population consisted of the beneficiaries of the UNDP/OSSHDF microcredit intervention fund in Osun state, Nigeria, between 2004 and 2008.

The sample consists of 78 trade associations drawn from the database of 117 trade associations that benefitted from the scheme. Overall, 1,500 individual beneficiaries were selected from a 4000 beneficiaries spread across the 30 local governments of Osun State.

The field of study included the pre-intervention questionnaire administered at the start of the program to collect baseline information and the comprehensive post-intervention questionnaire.

Instrument

Data for this study were collected from primary and secondary sources. The primary data were collected through questionnaires, structured interviews, and focus group discussions. The key variables measured were the impact of microcredit loans on

- i. the business's asset base and
- ii. income generating activities

Descriptive statistics, i.e., frequency distribution and percentages, were used in the data analysis. Quantitative techniques were used to measure and analyze the change in the asset base and income-generating activities (e.g., sales per day, cost of goods sold, and number of paid employees).

Results, Discussion, and Implications

Table 1: Effectiveness of Intervention on Some Components

LEVEL OF EFFECTIVENESS (N = 1468)											
S/N	Component of the area of Intervention	Not Effective		Effective		Very Effective		X ²	df	p-val	
		Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%				
		1	Strengthening of the 28 Asset Base (Business Expansion)	28	1.9	967	65.9				472
2	Promotion of income generating activities	33	2.2	953	65.0	481	32.8	865.64	2	0.001	

Strengthening of Asset Base

From Table 1, about sixty-six (65.9%) of respondents believed the intervention is effective in strengthening the asset base of their business, while another 32.2% rated it as very effective. This means that 98.1% rated the intervention effective, while less than 2% expressed a contrary view. This confirms that the intervention had a positive impact on business expansion. As previously discussed, 80% of the respondents got the loan more than once, out of which 20% got the loan six times. Therefore there is no doubt that the intervention opened access to increased funding with which the asset base could be strengthened and business could be expanded. This underscores the importance of capital availability in business expansion. This finding confirms earlier studies that microcredit intervention improves the asset base of the rural poor (Tria et al., 2022).

Promotion of income generation activities

Sixty five percent of the respondents indicated that the intervention was effective in promoting income-generating activities, while 32.8% believed it was very effective. Table 2 and 3 confirm the positive effect on income-generating activities on the post-intervention sales level and number of employees compared with pre-intervention levels. By positively impacting economic activities and increasing the employment rate, the intervention contributed to economic development to some extent. This corroborates the work of Orton et al. (2016), who found that group lending often results in the economic empowerment of the group and individual. The issue of impact on asset (capital) base was taken a step further by eliciting information on the sales and cost of goods sold before and after the intervention using paired test analysis. The following is the finding:

Table 2: Paired T-Test Analysis on the Impact of UNDP/OSSHDF Intervention on Beneficiaries’ Capital Base

	Before		Now		Tval	of	P-val
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD			
Estimate of sales per day	35,581.4	59,073	63,465.1	104,914.5	-3.77	85	0.001
Estimation of the cost of goods bought	8,000.2	10,161.6	12,905.3	16,890.9	-3.32	84	0.001

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

The results presented in **Table 4.** shows that the UNDP/OSSHDF intervention had a significant positive impact on beneficiaries’ capital base. The t-test analysis compared the pre- and post-intervention periods.

There was a significant difference in sales between the pre- and post-intervention period $t(85) = -3.77; P < 0.001$ and so also for the volume of goods bought $t(84) = -3.32; P < 0.001$.

The categories and number of employees before and after the intervention were also analyzed to measure the impact on the business growth.

Table 3: Paired t-test analysis on the category and number of beneficiaries’ employees

Employee Category	Before		Now		Tval	Df	P-val
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD			
Paid employee	2.17	0.98	3.67	0.51	-3.50	5	0.017
Apprentice	2.69	1.85	2.68	1.01	0.00	15	1.00
Relative	1.50	0.89	2.00	0.92	-3.68	20	0.002

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

The component analysis of the intervention’s impact on loan beneficiaries’ income-generating activities revealed two main categories of employees. These include paid employees and family/relative. For paid employee, a significant difference was observed in the pre- and post-intervention data $t(5) = -3.50; P < 0.001$. A significant result was also observed for family/relative category of employee when compared on pre- and post- intervention data $t(20) = -3.68; P = 0.002$. These results corroborate the descriptive analysis, which revealed a significant impact of the intervention on the loan beneficiaries’ **income-generating** activities. This position was also confirmed during the FGD discussion.

According to Omitogun and Longe (2017), employment is key to economic development, and gross unemployment is one of one of the major characteristics of underdevelopment. By increasing employment of labour, the intervention must have contributed positively to rural and economic development.

Hypothesis One

Microcredit does not lead to an improvement in beneficiaries’ asset base. To test this hypothesis, two sets of data were compared using pre- and post-intervention period as the asset base indicator. The initial capital of the business was compared with its present worth to establish any significant difference. The descriptive statistics are summarized in Table 4.

Table 4.: Paired-Samples t-test of Capital Change

Variable	N	Mean	Std D	Tval	Df	Pval
Initial business capital	84	35,5121	62934	-4.437	87	0.001*
Present worth of the business	88	76,080	116883			

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

*Statistically significant. P<0.001 revealed significant difference between the initial capital and present worth of the business. The analysis was performed at 0.05 level of significance. The result obtained $t(87) = 4.437$ is greater than the critical value of 1.96 required to make the result significant at the 0.05 level. With this result, a significant difference exists between beneficiaries’ initial capital and the business’s present worth.

Pearson’s product moment correlation analysis also established a positive correlation between the initial capital and present worth of the beneficiaries’ business $r(87) = 0.698; <0.001$. Two sets of results corroborate the positive impact of UNDP/OSSHF intervention on beneficiaries’ asset base. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternate hypothesis of the significant impact of UNDP/OSSUF intervention on the beneficiaries’ asset base is confirmed and accepted

Hypothesis Two

Microcredit does not promote income generating activities of beneficiaries.

In testing this hypothesis, responses to item on the extent to which the intervention has promoted income-generating activities of the beneficiaries were subjected to Chi-square analysis. The result is presented in Table 5 below:

The chi-square analysis is shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Effectiveness of intervention on income-generating activities (Group B)

Level of Effectiveness	Observed Freq	%	Expected	Residual
Not Effective	33	2.2	489	-456

Effective	953	64.9	489	464
Very Effective	481	32.9	489	-8.0
Total	1467	100		

Source: Field Survey, 2024. (X²=865.64; df =2; p<0.001.)

The table indicates the significant positive impact of the intervention on income generating activities of the beneficiaries X² (2) =865.64; df =2; p<0.001 respectively.

The null hypothesis which states that UNDP/OSSH intervention has no significant impact on income generating activities of beneficiaries is rejected and the alternate hypothesis accepted. Thus, we conclude that the intervention had significant impact on the beneficiaries’ income generating activities.

Conclusion

The above analysis, which compared the pre- and post-intervention states, established that the intervention was successful in strengthening the asset base and promoting the beneficiaries’ income-generating activities.

Recommendations

Microcredit organizations should be required to collect data from their clients on entry, which could be used as baseline information for later impact assessment. Impact assessment should be institutionalized and be an ongoing exercise rather than a one-off post-mortem event. This is because of its usefulness in facilitating a periodic review of activities that would bring to light necessary corrections, particularly in the methodology of the ongoing project. This is of tremendous importance to all stakeholders, including; clients, donors, microfinance institutions, and the community, because it is an important determinant of the success of the intervention.

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